

Excess Free Energy and Enthalpy of Mixing of Cyclohexane-Acetic Acid System at 25°

D. G. RAO*

Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006, Assam

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An attempt has been made to evaluate liquid phase activity coefficients free energy and enthalpy of mixing of cyclohexane acetic acid system at 25°. and to compare them with the reported values Chemical theory of Dolezolek and UNIFAC methods were used for this purpose.

The necessity of measuring/evaluating enthalpy of mixing and other thermodynamic properties, such as activity coefficients, free energy of mixing etc. of various systems in chemical engineering design need not be overemphasised, particularly more so with systems that have immediate industrial relevance. Cyclohexane-acetic acid is one such system which is normally encountered in the liquid phase auto-oxidation of cyclohexane in acetic acid medium to make adipic acid. In view of its industrial importance, the physicochemical and thermodynamic properties of the mixture have been well studied and reported¹⁻⁴.

Acetic acid, because of its nature in forming dimers, has a peculiar mixing behaviour exhibiting non-ideality. Attempts were made² to find specific volume effects between the dimer of acetic acid and solvent, and monomer-dimer interactions. Recently Lark *et al.*⁴ reported the excess properties at 25°. In the present communication, an attempt is made to calculate the activity coefficients in the liquid phase, and hence free energy of mixing at 25° by various methods. Use is made of the following approaches: (i) chemical theory of Dolezolek⁵ and (ii) UNIFAC method of Fradenslund *et al.*⁶. Since the chemical theory has not yielded good results in evaluating excess heats of mixing, the approach of 'two step process of mixing' of Scatchard⁷ is used for this purpose.

Results and Discussion

Chemical theory: According to this theory, the molecules in a solvent interact with each other to form new species (dimers or trimers etc.), and hence the non-ideality of the solution may be attributed to such chemical reactions, viz. association, solvation etc. The theory sufficiently accounts for positive and negative deviations from ideality, and can be used for predicting the non-ideal behaviour provided the equilibrium constant for such chemical reactions viz. dimerisation or solvation is known. Unfortunately, this has to be measured experimentally which

limits its application as a useful tool for making predictions. However, for pure acetic acid Affspring *et al.*² reported the dimerisation constant at 20° (K_{20}^0) and enthalpy of dimerisation (ΔH) to be 62 and -6210 cal mol⁻¹ respectively, and estimated (approximately) the dimerisation constant at infinite dilution in cyclohexane (K_{20}^∞) to be 400000. From the values of K_{20}^0 and K_{20}^∞ , it is possible to estimate K_{20} at any mole fraction of cyclohexane (x_1) as follows²:

$$\log K_{20} = x_2 \log K_{20}^0 + x_1 \log K_{20}^\infty - 2x_1x_2 \quad (1)$$

The dimerisation constant (K) at any other temperature can be evaluated by:

$$\ln \frac{K}{K_{20}} = \frac{\Delta H}{R} \left(\frac{1}{273+20} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \quad (2)$$

From a knowledge of K , it is possible to calculate the liquid phase activity coefficients (γ_1, γ_2) by the expressions⁵,

$$\gamma_a = \frac{(1+K)(1+KZ^2)}{(1+KZ)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_1 = 1 + KZ^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } Z = \frac{(1+4Kx_1x_2)^{1/2} - 1}{2Kx_1} \quad (5)$$

γ_1 and γ_2 are activity coefficients of cyclohexane and acetic acid respectively. Table 1 presents data of various above quantities, and Fig. 1 shows the

TABLE 1— K AND Z DATA AT 25° FOR VARIOUS VALUES OF x_1

x_1	K	Z
0.1	82.38	0.275 3
0.2	143.48	0.150 4
0.3	274.01	0.086 4
0.4	573.77	0.049 0
0.5	1 317.36	0.026 8
0.6	3 316.43	0.013 9
0.7	9 154.56	0.006 7
0.8	27 708.00	0.003 0
0.9	91 954.10	0.001 1

*Present Address: CFTRI Regional Centre, Habshiguda, Uppal Road, Hyderabad-500 007.

Fig. 1. Plots of activity coefficient vs mole fraction : (—) by UNIFAC and (---) by chemical theory ; (x) reported data (Ref. 4).

values of activity coefficients. The agreement between the reported values of Lark *et al.*⁴ and those calculated by chemical theory seems to be fairly good. The free energy (G^E) and enthalpy (H^E) of mixing are given by

$$G^E = RT(x_1 \ln \gamma_1 + x_2 \ln \gamma_2) \quad (6)$$

$$H^E = -RT^2 \left[\frac{d(G^E/RT)}{dT} \right]_x \quad (7)$$

H^E was evaluated by equation (7) by differentiating equation (6) after substituting for $\ln \gamma_1$ and $\ln \gamma_2$ from equations (3)–(6) as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d(G^E/RT)}{dT} &= \left[\frac{2AKZ + Z^2}{1 + KZ^2} + \frac{x_2}{1 + K} - \frac{2x_2(AK + Z)}{1 + KZ} \right] \frac{dK}{dT} \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where, } A = \frac{x_2}{K(1 + 4Kx_1x_2)^{1/2}} - \frac{(1 + 4Kx_1x_2)^{1/2} - 1}{2K^2x_1} \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dK}{dT} = K(\Delta H/RT^2) \quad (10)$$

Figs. 2 and 3 show data on G^E and H^E . It may be noted that the excess free energy values calculated by chemical method and that reported by Lark *et al.*⁴ seem to be in reasonably good agreement. However, the excess enthalpy values calculated by chemical method do not match with the reported values (Fig. 3). Hence, an alternative approach of Scatchard⁷ was made who considered that mixing as a two-step process, viz. mixing of two components

Fig. 2. Plots of excess free energy (G^E) vs mole fraction : (—) by UNIFAC and (---) by chemical theory ; (x) reported data (Ref. 4).

at constant volume followed by an expansion or contraction to attain the initial pressure⁹.

$$H^E = E_m^v(1 + \alpha T) \quad (11)$$

where α is thermal expansivity and is given by

$$\alpha = \sum (v_i \alpha_i) \quad (12)$$

$$E_m^v = V_m(\delta_1 - \delta_2)^2 v_1 v_2 \quad (13)$$

where, E_m^v is energy of mixing at constant volume, v_1 and v_2 are volume fractions of cyclohexane and acetic acid in the solution, and δ_1 and δ_2 the solubility parameters of cyclohexane and acetic acid which are given by

$$\delta_i = (\Delta E_i/V_i)^{1/2} \quad (14)$$

where E_i is the energy of vaporisation (E_1 for cyclohexane and E_2 for acetic acid) and V the molar volume.

The data required for various parameters in equations (12) and (14) are presented in Table 2.

The data required in equations (11)–(14) are presented in Table 3. Using equation (11), the H^E

Fig. 3. Plots of excess enthalpy (H^E) vs mole fraction : (—) by UNIFAC, (---) by chemical theory (eqns. 7 and 8) and (-.-) by two-step process of mixing of Scatchard (Ref. 7).

TABLE 2— α , δ , V AND ΔE_i^* VALUES

Component	α deg ⁻¹	δ (cal/ml) ^{1/2}	V ml/mol	ΔE_i^* cal/mol
Cyclohexane	0.001 234	8.2 ^a	108.51	7705
Acetic acid	0.001 071	10.789 ^b	57.48	6701

*At 25°. ^aRef. 9 ^bCalculated by equation (14).

was calculated and is presented in Fig. 3. The agreement between the reported values and the calculated ones is fairly good.

UNIFAC method: The UNIFAC method⁶ is an altogether different approach to evaluate the liquid phase activity coefficients, and is based on the functional group contributions. It is purely a theoretical approach without necessitating any experi-

TABLE 3— E_m^V AND H^E DATA AT 25**

x_1	α deg ⁻¹	ϕ_1	ϕ_2	V_m ml/mol	E_m^V cal/mol	H^E (calcd) cal/mol
0.1	0.001 087	0.173 3	0.826 6	62.58	60.513	80.131
0.2	0.001 104	0.298 0	0.702 0	67.69	95.577	127.026
0.3	0.001 120	0.447 2	0.552 8	77.79	129.807	173.149
0.4	0.001 136	0.557 2	0.442 7	77.89	129.690	173.623
0.5	0.001 152	0.653 7	0.346 3	83.00	126.827	170.407
0.6	0.001 169	0.739 0	0.261 0	88.09	114.687	154.650
0.7	0.001 185	0.815 0	0.185 0	93.20	94.852	128.360
0.8	0.001 201	0.883 0	0.116 9	98.30	68.490	93.020
0.9	0.001 217	0.944 4	0.055 6	103.41	36.650	49.950

** $\alpha_1 = 0.001234$ deg⁻¹ $\alpha_2 = 0.001071$ deg⁻¹.

mental data and is applicable to a wide range of mixtures exhibiting either positive or negative deviations from Raoult's law. The activity coefficient is considered to be a combination of two parts: combinatorial part and residual part. The method provides a simple procedure for calculating activity coefficients in terms of constants reflecting the size and surface area of individual functional groups (combinatorial part), and parameters representing energetic interactions between the groups (residual part). The size parameter (R), area parameter (Q) and group interaction parameter (a_{m-n}) for various groups were evaluated and documented in literature^{6,10} from the pure component molecular data and phase equilibrium data of eightythree different group interactions in the temperature region 275–400 K.

Acetic acid is considered to consist of one CH₃ group and one COOH group whereas cyclohexane six CH₂ groups. The values of various functional groups in the present study are follows: $R_{CH_3} = 0.9011$, $Q_{CH_3} = 0.843$, $a_{CH_3-COOH} = a_{CH_2-COOH} = 663.50$, $R_{CH_2} = 0.6744$, $Q_{CH_2} = 0.540$, $a_{COOH-CH_3} = 315.13$, $R_{COOH} = 1.3013$, $Q_{COOH} = 1.224$.

The activity coefficients and hence free energy of mixing were evaluated by the UNIFAC method as detailed by Fredenslund *et al.*⁶. The calculations are quite elaborative and are presented below.

The activity coefficient may be written as :

$$\ln \gamma_i = \ln \gamma_i^C + \ln \gamma_i^R \quad \text{Combinatorial Residual} \quad (A1)$$

$$\text{where, } \ln \gamma_i^C = \ln \frac{\phi_i}{x_i} + \frac{z}{2} q_i \ln \frac{\theta_i}{\phi_i} + l_i - \frac{\phi_i}{x_i} \sum_j x_j l_j \quad (A2)$$

$$\text{and } \ln \gamma_i^R = \sum_k v_k^{(i)} [\ln \Gamma_k - \ln \Gamma_k^{(i)}] \quad \text{all groups} \quad (A3)$$

$$l_i = \frac{z}{2} (r_i - q_i) - (r_i - 1) \quad (A4)$$

$$\theta_i = \frac{q_i x_i}{\sum_j q_j x_j} \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_i = \frac{r_i x_i}{\sum_j r_j x_j} \quad (A5)$$

$$q_i = \frac{v_i Q_i}{\sum_j v_j Q_j} \quad \text{and} \quad r_i = \frac{v_i R_i}{\sum_j v_j R_j} \quad (A6)$$

$$\ln \Gamma_k = Q_k [1 - \ln \sum_m \theta_m \Psi_{mk} - \sum_m (\theta_m \Psi_{km} / \sum_n \theta_n \Psi_{nm})] \quad (A7)$$

$$\theta_m = \frac{Q_m X_m}{\sum_n Q_n X_n} \quad (A8)$$

$$\Psi_{mn} = \exp - (a_{mn}/T) \quad (A9)$$

where, Γ_k is the group residual activity coefficient, and $\Gamma_k^{(i)}$ is the residual activity coefficient of group k in a reference solution containing only molecules of type i . Equation (A7) also holds for $\ln \Gamma_k^{(i)}$. X_m is the mole fraction of group m in the whole mixture. v_k^i always an integer, is the number of groups of type k in molecule i .

Hence for system cyclohexane (1)–acetic acid (2), if following is the representation of groups

CH₂ – group 1B

CH₃ – group 1A

COOH – group n

then, $\nu_{1B}^{(i)} = 6$, $\nu_{1A}^{(2)} = 1$ and $\nu_n^{(2)} = 1$

$X_{1B} = 1.0$ for pure cyclohexane

$X_{1A} = 0.5$ and $X_n = 0.5$ for pure acetic acid

$$X_{1B} = \frac{6 \times 0.1}{(6 \times 0.1) + (1 \times 0.9) + (1 \times 0.9)} = 0.25$$

$$X_{1A} = \frac{1 \times 0.9}{(6 \times 0.1) + (1 \times 0.9) + (1 \times 0.9)} = 0.375$$

$$X_n = \frac{1 \times 0.9}{(6 \times 0.1) + (1 \times 0.9) + (1 \times 0.9)} = 0.375$$

The above three values are for $x_1 = 0.1$, i.e. when mole fraction of cyclohexane is 0.1. The method follows further as per the procedure given by equations (A1) to (A9). In the original UNIFAC model, the value of the coordination parameter (z) was taken to be a constant 10.0, and considered to be independent of temperature. However, later on, Skjold-

Jorgensen *et al.*^{1*} suggested to incorporate temperature correction for z and called it as $z(T)$ in the UNIFAC calculations, where

$$\xi(T) = 35.2 - 0.1272T + 0.00014 T^2 \quad (A10)$$

The results are presented in Figs. 1 and 2. The predictions are fairly good, but the values are lower than that reported⁴. The enthalpy of mixing was evaluated by the procedure adopted by Dang and Tasslos¹¹. The results are presented in Fig. 3. Predictions are good but higher than the reported values.

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